

Educating for the Future: Engaging Students with Robotics and Intelligent Machines

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Abstract— This paper presents a specialized course developed by the Università Politecnica delle Marche to introduce secondary school students to robotics and intelligent machines. In response to national initiatives under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) aimed at improving career guidance in the transition from school to university, the course engaged students aged 16-18 in both theoretical and practical sessions. The course, titled "Robotica al servizio dell'uomo," covered foundational topics in robotics and artificial intelligence (AI), including the programming of robotic systems and their applications. A key component was a visit to the university's robotics laboratories, where students participated in hands-on activities and acquired insight into university life and academic opportunities.

Keywords—robotics, education, secondary school, university

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, robotics has advanced well beyond its traditional industrial role, now playing a crucial part in everyday life, science, and multiple industries [1], [2]. As robotics and intelligent machines reshape the world, it is essential to prepare the next generation to engage with these technologies [3]. For secondary school students nearing important educational and career decisions, understanding the opportunities and challenges in robotics and Artificial Intelligence (AI) is vital. This knowledge will help them make informed career choices, especially as many future roles will require specialized technical skills and critical thinking. However, despite the growing presence of robotics in daily life, many students are still unaware of the latest technological developments and career paths in this field. Many students are not fully aware of the importance of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education or how these skills are directly relevant to the rapidly evolving field of robotics and AI. Recognizing the importance of this issue, Italian universities have been tasked with addressing such educational gap, particularly considering national initiatives aimed at improving career guidance and educational transitions. In response to the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), part of the NextGenerationEU programme, the Ministry of University and Research (MUR) and the Ministry of Education (MIM) have now required universities to implement orientation courses. These courses, as mandated by Ministerial Decree No. 934/2022 and Director's Decree No. 1452/2022, are to be delivered through agreements with secondary schools and must consist of a minimum of 15 hours of instruction for students in their third, fourth, and fifth years [4]. In response to this challenge, the Università Politecnica

delle Marche organized a specialized course aimed at introducing secondary school students to robotics and its evolution toward autonomous and intelligent machines. The primary goal of the course was to engage students with the latest developments in these fields, raise awareness of the underlying science and technology, and guide them in preparing for future challenges. The course also emphasized critical thinking about the societal and ethical implications of robotics, encouraging students to reflect on how intelligent machines might shape the future workforce, healthcare, and everyday life. Outreach activities such as this play a vital role in bridging the gap between secondary education and the engineering and technology-related careers [5],[6]. Well-structured outreach programs can help guide students toward informed decisions by providing a deeper understanding of potential educational and professional pathways [7]. Among the approaches to these experiences [8], [9], the proposed course represents a multidimensional intervention, which combines both pedagogical and experiential components [8].

II. COURSE STRUCTURE AND CONTENT

A. Participants

The course was designed for students attending the 3rd, 4th, 5th year of the secondary schools (age 16–18). Four secondary schools participated in the program, three of which had a STEM curriculum, and one had a SSH (Social Sciences and Humanities) curriculum. Each school engaged one classroom with the course. A total of 106 students completed the course.

B. Course delivery and content

The course, titled "Robotica al servizio dell'uomo: dall'autonomia all'intelligenza" ("Robotics in Service of Humanity: from autonomy to intelligence"), was designed to provide students with a comprehensive understanding of robotics and intelligent machines. It was delivered during regular school hours, and consisted in three lectures lasting four hours each, and a laboratory tutorial lasting three hours. Lectures were held at the participating schools, while the tutorial was hosted at the university's laboratories. The course was led by three university professors, who structured the sessions to combine foundational knowledge with hands-on activities, ensuring students gained both conceptual and practical insights. Topics of the course included the basic notions about robotics, the types of robots currently available and under development, and how robot's behavior is programmed. These theoretical discussions laid the groundwork for students to understand the role of robotics in modern society and the technological challenges in designing and deploying such systems. The visit to the facilities of the

university, engaged students in hands-on activities, such as basic python programming using the Google Colab service [10] to evaluate the inference of pre-trained deep learning models for object detection. This gave them the opportunity to expand their understanding of how robots are designed, built, and operated. An additional component of the course was the introduction to university life. Students were provided with information about the academic programs, facilities, and the structure of the university system in both Italy and abroad. This aspect of the course was designed to help students envision their potential future in higher education.

C. Feedback collection

Students completed two questionnaires. One assessed their preparedness for post-graduation decisions and was administered only once, at the end of the whole course. Another one evaluated the knowledge they acquired, focusing on the basic robotics notions (robotics definitions), on related topics like dynamic systems and unstructured environments (advanced notions) and on robot programming. It was administered both before the start of the activities (BL) and after the end of the activities (PT).

III. RESULTS

The effectiveness of the course was measured through the survey questions aimed at assessing students' perceptions of how well the course prepared them for post-graduation decisions, the knowledge they gained, and their overall satisfaction with the experience. When asked, "Do you feel that, after this orientation course, you are more prepared to make an informed post-graduation choice?" 75.4% of students responded yes. In response to the question, "Do you feel that the orientation course provided you with information, knowledge, and skills you were previously unaware of?", 89.2% of students answered yes. Student satisfaction with specific aspects of the course was also evaluated using a Likert-type scale ranging from "completely satisfied" to "not satisfied at all". For the clarity of the presentation, 60% of students were completely or very satisfied, 38.5% were quite satisfied. Regarding the presence of laboratory sessions, 63.1% of the students were completely or very satisfied of the laboratory sessions and the rest of them were quite satisfied. The overall satisfaction with the course showed 64.6% of students were completely or very satisfied, 26.2% were quite satisfied. Figure 1 reports the share of students' correct answers to the questionnaire about basic robotics definitions, advanced notions related to robotics and intelligent machines, and about robot programming. Results suggest that the course was effective in increasing knowledge about those topics.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The results from the survey indicate that the course effectively achieved its primary objectives of increasing students' preparedness for post-graduation decisions and enhancing their knowledge of robotics and intelligent machines. The high percentage of students who felt more prepared to make informed decisions after completing the course highlights the importance of integrating specialized educational programs into the school curriculum. Moreover, the fact that most of the students reported gaining new information and skills underscores the value of combining theoretical instruction with hands-on experience. The practical component, including the visit to the university labs, provided an engaging and tangible connection to real-world applications of robotics, which likely contributed to the high

Fig. 1: percentage of correct answers to knowledge questions at BL (before activities) and PT (after the activities ended).

levels of satisfaction reported in both the theoretical and practical sections. Future implementations will include a more detailed assessment of the course impact, as well as the evaluation of the long-term effect on students' academic and career choices. Finally, this course serves as an example of a multidimensional intervention under the PNRR combining guidance, education, and experiential learning. By focusing on educational transitions and career guidance such interventions play a key role in fostering student interest in STEM careers, thus strengthening Italy's commitment to sustainable development, technological innovation, and resilience in education, key to the country's recovery and future stability.

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